

1 Cervical epithelial organoids from individuals with cervical cancer.

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total gene expression in organoid cell culture to describe in an unbiased fashion the
8 transcriptional landscape of the normal cervix and if the primary tumor in cervical cancer. We report here
9 loss of immune receptor *Flrt2* expression in cervical cancer organoids. *Flrt2* silencing in the cervical
10 cancer organoids was accompanied by activation of the TLR signaling adapter *Tril*.

11 Citations

12 1. Yamagishi, S., Hampel, F., Hata, K., Del Toro, D., Schwark, M., Kvachnina, E., Bastmeyer, M.,
13 Yamashita, T., Tarabykin, V., Klein, R. and Egea, J., 2011. FLRT2 and FLRT3 act as repulsive guidance
14 cues for Unc5-positive neurons. The EMBO journal, 30(14), p.2920.

15 GSE246571
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28